

Excellent peripheries for a strong
European Research Area

7.2 Project Website

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HEI	Higher Education Institution
R&I	Research & Innovation
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report constitutes the deliverable “D7.2 Project Website” of the EXPER project. This is one of four deliverables associated with Work Package (WP) 7 “Dissemination”. The document has been prepared by Consulta Europa and reviewed by the project Steering Committee (SC).

This report is a comprehensive document which outlines the website to be used throughout the project in the dissemination and outreach of the activities and products (deliverables and communication materials) under development. The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a description of the framework and backbone of the main public channel for dissemination of the project.

To have a consistent image and identity across platforms, a fixed visual identity comprising the project logo, colours and templates has been developed for the project. This ensures a uniquely identifiable and easy-to-recall image for the project across all platforms. The visual identity will be transversally applied to all the communication tools and channels that will be used in the EXPER project.

The public website will contain information regarding the project, its results, a biannual newsletter, a social media feed, an agenda with events and conferences, press news, and so on. These tools have been selected in line with the communication objectives and target audiences of the project.

1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1. THE PROJECT

EXPER will set the basis for a European University Alliance which realises integrated cooperation between the research and innovation (R&I) dimension with the education and training dimension. In this way, EXPER will deploy a community-based approach to outline a modernization strategy for the Widening Universities which involves representatives of the surrounding ecosystem.

The aim of EXPER is to enhance the scientific excellence and innovation capacity of the partnering universities and their role as drivers of economic and social transformation in their territories with a focus on research fields addressing challenges and opportunities offered by the blue economy and circular economy.

The project consists in supporting the institutional transformation of University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ES) and Azores University (PT) through capacity-building activities and through international cooperation with the leading Universities of Rostock University (DE) and Calabria (IT).

1.2. THE CONSORTIUM

EXPER project is managed by a consortium of 10 partners and 1 affiliated entity from 4 European Union countries (Spain, Portugal, Germany and Italy). In particular, the consortium counts on the participation of representatives of R&I ecosystems of two Widening regions, the Azores, and Canary Islands, including two Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), governmental institutions and one small and medium enterprise (SME), two HEIs from Germany and Italy and one technological consultancy from Germany.

The consortium is listed in Table 1.

Table 1. EXPER's consortium.

N°	Role	Shortname	Participant organisation name	Country
1	Coordinator	ULPGC	UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	ES
1.1	Affiliated Entity	FCPCT ULPGC	FUNDACION CANARIA PARQUE CIENTIFICO TECNOLOGICO DE LA UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA	ES
2	Beneficiary	UAc	UNIVERSIDADE DOS ACORES	PT
3	Beneficiary	UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA	IT
4	Beneficiary	SPEGC	SOCIEDAD DE PROMOCION ECONOMICA DE GRAN CANARIA SA	ES

5	Beneficiary	EMERGE	ASOCIACION CANARIA DE STARTUPS EMPRESAS DEBASE TECNOLOGICA E INVERSOIRES ANGELES	ES
6	Beneficiary	TERINOV	PCTTER ASSOCIACAO PARQUE DE CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA DA ILHA TERCEIRA	PT
7	Beneficiary	ATRINEO AG	ATRINEO AG	DE
8	Beneficiary	CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL	ES
9	Beneficiary	ITC	INSTITUTO TECNOLOGICO DE CANARIAS,S.A.	ES
10	Beneficiary	UROS	UNIVERSITAET ROSTOCK	DE

1.3. EXPER'S DISSEMINATION WP7

1.3.1. OBJECTIVES

WP 7: "Dissemination" responds to all project objectives since it aims at disseminating and transferring the outputs and results of all EXPER activities to its key stakeholders. The specific objectives of this WP are:

- to raise awareness among staff of EXPER HEI, citizens and representatives of surrounding ecosystems, on the role of HEI and of R&I in fostering regional development and addressing societal challenges
- to disseminate information on the project objectives, activities and expected results
- to raise awareness on the relevance of gender equality and diversity in R&I, of responsible research
- to foster the uptake of EXPER results and support their replication in other EU HEIs
- to inform about the preparation of an EXPER European University Alliance

1.3.2. VISUAL IDENTITY

The visual identity will be detailed under Deliverable 7.1 Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, including Communication Activities for month 6, March 2023. Nonetheless, the website will already start incorporating elements from the visual identity and the website will be continuously updated throughout the project.

The first and most important element to develop in order to have a consistent visual identity is the logo and the main colours and style that will be used throughout the project duration not only in dissemination and communication (D&C) materials but in all documents of the project (as in this deliverable), thus defining the project's identity and ensuring recognisability.

The website, then, will include the logo and the colours that has been developed and agreed by the Consortium (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Visual identity of EXPER project.

2 . WEBSITE

2 . 1 . WEBSITE DEVELOPMENT

The EXPER website has been created and developed in the first months of the project. This deliverable shows the main elements of the website that will be updated and adjusted throughout the project.

The website is accessible at the following address: <https://exper-project.eu/>. The website has been developed in English to be accessible to any kind of international and EU stakeholders. Its purpose is to act as the “vitrine” of the project and to get in touch with interested parties since the very beginning of the project. For EXPER’s website we have used corporate image and corporate colours of the project to build the graphic part of the website.

WordPress, a standard for website creation, and a Content Management System (CMS) has been used to develop the website. A CMS is a tool which helps you quickly to create and manage content for websites. It is frequently web-based and the best-known feature of these type of tools is its ability to add, update, or delete content.

WordPress was chosen as it is a popular open-source CMS utilized by a wide range of websites, including expert publications and e-commerce platforms. It is very flexible, capable of creating a functional website that can be edited and adjusted according to the project’s needs. It is particularly great at providing blogging features, with various plugins which allow users to extend their website functionalities.

The website, like other D&C material, will be a living space. It will be maintained, updated and further developed throughout the project to be as active and attractive as possible. For this reason, the website includes a section where to read regular news articles and another section with all social media platforms integrated. **All project partners will provide information for the publication of news on the website to CE.**

2 . 2 . STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The header and footer of the website will remain unchanged.

Figure 2. EXPER’s website header.

The header will include all different “categories” for the visitor to easily access their desired tab. The Header, with Corporate colours, will provide the Contact tab on the top, followed by the two main categories: About & Project. On a third level the remaining

categories such as Home, News, Events and Partners will be shown. EXPER's logo will appear on the left of the header with its acronym.

These main categories on the header might change as the project progresses and other information is deemed necessary to show. For example, a section called "Resources" for deliverables and publications has been created but will not show on the website until these products are created.

Figure 3. EXPER's website footer.

The footer will present a box to subscribe to the EXPER Newsletter by signing up with an e-mail address and information regarding Data Protection. A PDF with the Data Protection Information will show when clicking the link found at "here". The mechanism behind the newsletter follows the WordPress plug-in to send the emails. Visitors will be able to check the most recent updates related to this project. Links to the main sections on the platform will be provided, thus the newsletter will be a short brief and updated website overview.

To the right of the subscription box the visitor will find the main categories of the website to directly access them. Underneath, the most recent news will show.

The website main tabs will be detailed in the sub-chapters below.

2.2.1. HOME PAGE

On the EXPER website's home page, the header is the same as described in the introductory part of Chapter 2.2 "Structure of the Website".

The "Home" Page counts with:

- The header.

- The project's title and acronym are displayed accompanied by the logo. This is a sliding section that can show as many images related to the project as needed. At the moment no more images have been added. The Learn more button will re-direct the user to the "Project" tab.

Figure 4. Home page section I: title.

- Short description of the project .

Introducing EXPER. Find out now!

EXPER – ‘Excellent peripheries for a strong European Research Area’ is a Research and Innovation Action financed by Horizon Europe. It aims at the institutional transformation of two universities from EU Outermost Regions – the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain) and University of Azores (Azores, Portugal). Both universities will learn through capacity building and international cooperation from the leading Universities of Rostock (Germany) and Calabria (Italy).

Supporting research and innovation excellence

The aim of EXPER is to enhance the scientific excellence and innovation capacity of the partnering universities and their role as drivers of economic and social transformation in their territories with a focus on research fields addressing challenges and opportunities offered by the blue economy and circular economy.

The project consists in supporting the institutional transformation of University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and Azores University through capacity building activities and through international cooperation with the leading Universities of Rostock University (DE) and Calabria (IT).

[Read More](#)

Figure 5. Home page II: project description.

- EXPER project overview with the most important information of the project.

Figure 6. Home page III: EXPER overview.

- A summary of coming events will be shown. At this moment the events also deemed “important” are showing. With the progression of the project and more events being organised by EXPER, this will not be necessary.

Events

Figure 7. Home page IV: Events.

- The latest news.

Latest news

Figure 8. Home page V: News.

The partners and their roles.

Partners

Figure 9. Home page VI: Partners

A social media feed.

Social media

Figure 10. Home page VII: Social media.

The footer.

2.2.2. ABOUT

The Information provided in the section “About”, is related to explaining the challenge that EXPER is addressing, the strategy or approach the project is following and its objectives:

The Challenge

Universities play a key role as aggregators of different actors in EU regional innovation systems and as connectors with other organisations abroad. In this context, Outermost Regions, such as Azores and Canary Islands, face greater challenges in terms of R&I modernisation due to structural handicaps and geographical location such as lack of proximity with excellence Higher education institutions.

EXPER Approach

To overcome the previous challenges, EXPER will deploy a community-based approach to establish and implement a modernisation strategy of its two Widening Universities – University of Las Palmas (ULPGC) and University of Azores (UAz).

The institutional transformation of these universities will be also achieved through peer-learning and cooperation with the leading Universities of Rostock (UROS) and Calabria (UNICAL). Capacity building will focus especially on blue and green economy and circular economy, which have sectors of high R&I potential for EU Outermost Regions.

Figure 11. About tab I.

Specific objectives

The project specific objectives are to:

- Raise the excellence profile of ULPGC and UAc and increase their attractiveness towards local and international talents.
- Design and plan their institutional transformation with the proactive engagement of stakeholders from their regional R&I systems.
- Promote capacity building activities to learn from best practices from UROS and UNICAL.
- Set the basis for a new European University Alliance.

Figure 12. About tab II.

2.2.3. PROJECT

Figure 13. Project tab I.

Figure 14. Project tab section II: EXPER main pillars.

The project page will show the main pillars of the project, and below them, the user can select one of the four remaining sections of the tab: the pillars to be back at the top, the work packages (WPs), the expected impacts and the partners.

Figure 15. Project tab section III: Buttons.

The WPs' section describes each WP's objectives and tasks that will be carried out in the project as well as who is the partner leading each.

Work Packages

WP1 - Regional ecosystems assessment and cooperation models
Leader: ULPGC

This WP will aim at assessing regional ecosystems of the HEI widening partners to identify barriers at institutional/regional and national level which hamper HEIs' potential role as driver of regional development and competitiveness. On the other side, activities under this WP will aim at collecting knowledge and assessing existing cooperation models and practices ...

WP1

WP2 - Co-designing modernization with surrounding ecosystems
Leader: ULPGC

This WP aims at gathering all relevant actors in each Widening ecosystems and co-design Modernization strategies for transformations of Widening HEI based on research and innovation ...

WP2

Figure 16. Project tab section IV: Work Packages.

The expected impact of the project is described and will be updated throughout the project with infographics showing the progression of the project activities and its real impact. At the moment, only the main impacts are shown.

Expected Impacts

- Increased science and innovation capacities for all actors in the Research & Innovation (R&I) system in widening countries.
- Structural changes leading to a modernized and more competitive R&I systems in eligible countries.
- Reformed R&I systems and institutions leading also to increased attractiveness and retention of research talents.
- Higher participation success in Horizon Europe and more consortium leadership roles and improved outreach to international scale for all actors.
- Stronger linkages between academia and business and improved career permeability.
- Strengthened role of the Higher Education sector in research and innovation.
- Greater involvement of regional actors in R&I process.

Figure 17. Project tab section V: impact.

The Partners' section can also be reached by selecting it on the footer. The Consortium is detailed in this section, with the partner's logos, contact information and their roles in the project.

Partners

Figure 18. Project tab section VI: Partners.

By selecting each partner, the blue circle will move and the following box will appear with the partner's information (logo, title, description and social media).

Figure 19. Partner's social media.

2.2.4. NEWS

This page gathers information related to the news published by EXPER and Digital Newspapers. To the right of the News the viewer can find the Newsletter subscription box. The news can be shared by selecting the social media desired on the left.

Facebook Twitter LinkedIn

Do not miss any update!
Receive our latest news.
Enter your email address
Subscribe
Yes, according to the GDPR I agree to EXPER keeping me informed with the biannual newsletter. Learn more about our Privacy Policy.

The ULPCC raises half a million euros with the EXPER project to boost research and innovation capabilities

Figure 20. News

2.2.5. EVENTS

The events page shows the Agenda for EXPER's events.

Figure 21. Events

There are three categories: Important, upcoming and finished. The important events can be manually added to the Important category. When selecting each event, a pop-up window will emerge with all the event’s information (description, date, time, place, etc.):

Figure 22. Emergent window of events.

2.2.6. CONTACT

Finally, the last page that can be found at the top of the header has information regarding how to contact the EXPER team. It provides the address, phone, and email to reach the WP7 leader, CE, but also to reach the EXPER's email managed by CE: info@exper-project.eu and EXPER's social media.

In addition, a contact form is available to send comments, questions, or suggestions. To fill out this form, the visitor needs to fill in their name, email, and message. In line with the website's privacy policy, the email address of the visitor is required in order to answer their concerns. All tabs are obligatory to fill in. This message will be directly redirected to EXPER's emails, and the queries will be answered as soon as possible.

Contact

Tel: (+34) 828 041 258
Email: info@exper-project.eu
Location: Leopoldo Matos 16, bajo 35006,
Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Spain

Full name

Email

Your Message *

Submit

Figure 23. Contact section.

2.3. EXTRA MATERIAL

The section described below have been designed and created in the WordPress. However, they will not be shown until later in the project when they are needed.

2.3.1. RESULTS

Under this tab information regarding the results of the project can be found. This section will not be visible until the materials are finalised and ready to share to the public.

Deliverables

Figure 24. Resources section I: deliverables.

All public deliverables or EXPER public documents will be updated here for visitors to download if needed.

Communication materials

Figure 25. Resources section II & III: Communication materials & Publications.

On the communication materials section the leaflet, roll-up and other printable materials will be shown and will also be available for download.

In the Publications section, a list of EXPER publications will be shared.

Each section will only be visible when material is produced.

2.3.2. GALLERY

The Gallery is a repository where to find albums of images. This section has been created but will not be shown until there is a solid database of images from EXPER events that the consortium wants to share.

Figure 26. Gallery

When accessing the gallery, albums can be accessed by clicking on them at the top.

Figure 27. Content Gallery.

This will re-direct the user to the gallery of each album:

Explore albums >

Dissemination Materials

Figure 28. Explore albums at the gallery.

2.3.2. UNIVERSITY ALLIANCE

As the generation of a European University Alliance (EUA) is transversal to EXPER, an extra tab has been already created for its future use if considered by the Consortium.

One of EXPER project's objectives was to create a new EUA between the universities involved in the Consortium: University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, University of Azores, University of Calabria and University of Rostock. Here a definition of an EUA is given and some examples of already existing UA. In the future, the newly created EXPER EUA can be shown here.

What is an University Alliance?

A University Alliance is a collaboration of technical and professional institutions that fosters growth and innovation through research, education and entrepreneurship.

The institutions that make up the University Alliance are pioneers when it comes to their interactions with business partners and possible talents.

Figure 29. University Alliance page.

Other University Alliances:

Figure 30. Other University Alliances section.

3 . IMAGES

The images on the website have been downloaded from Freepik and Envato, both image libraries with a license under the WP leader Consulta Europa.

Throughout the project, pictures will be taken at different events as well as for dissemination purposes that might also be used for the website.

4 . WEBSITE NEXT STEPS

The website will be promoted on social media and offline channels in order to engage with stakeholders, citizens and media.

It will be managed by Consulta Europa that will regularly ask the partners for updates on their work to share it on the website. On that sense, the website will work as a joint internet location/space where information regarding all aspects of EXPER can be found, especially those of results. In the following months, the web will be prepared for mobile devices with a responsive design.

The website will be regularly updated when events are scheduled, news articles are published, an important milestone has been achieved, etc. However, once every two months before and/or during the Progress meetings, the CE team will check with the partners their dissemination effort in case something is missing. CE will also ask them for updates for the website.

The website structure might also suffer changes as the project progresses and new needs are identified.

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